

Mass Media: Veritable Tool in Curbing Corruption for Sustainable Peace and Development in Nigeria?

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Abstract:

This paper focuses on the role of the mass media in curbing corruption to aid sustainable peace and development in Nigeria. Transparency International, an independent global watch on corruption ranks Nigeria among the five most corrupt nations in the world, an inglorious record that has stunted growth, peace and development in all areas in Nigeria. These are impediments to national development, especially, in the vision for Nigeria becoming one of the 20 most developed economies in the world by the year 2020. This paper employed agenda –setting theory and observational learning and imitation behavior theory, and concluded that the fight against corruption must be one of the topmost priorities of the government at all levels in Nigeria. The media should be encouraged to develop and enforce adequate standards of conduct regarding their professional competence and their objectivity so that they would avoid any temptations of accepting gifts, envelopes, fare or any other support that would interfere with their free reporting. And it recommended that since, there are enough rules to prevent corruption, the application of such rules should be applied in a blanket form, and not randomly, this will instill fear into all the stakeholders. And the Organizations engaged in the fight against corruption can use media as allies and as vehicle for their work to improve their chances of success, their effectiveness and their sustainability.

Key Words: Mass Media, Corruption, Agenda-setting Theory and Brown Envelope

Introduction

The mass media has become a very powerful tool in the society; the public has become really dependent on the media to keep informed, educated and entertained. The strength of the mass media also lies in the society as it is from the society that they derive the information which they in turn relate to the public. The relationship between the mass media and society is therefore interdependent. The mass media referred to in this study are the print media, electronic media and social media.

The Nigerian Media and corruption in Nigeria just like in other society, the mass media transmit ideas and new information to a target audience. This implies that they are responsible for most of the adjustments in the behavioral pattern of people in the society. The influence of the mass media extends to almost every segment of the society that is exposed to their programmes. In other words, the press serves as an agent of change, and as the watchdog of the society is expected to play a part in ensuring transparency and accountability in government as well as contribute to the efforts of crime-fighting institutions to curb corruption in the country (Nwuneli, [1990; Nwosu, [2004).

There is also need to focus the anti-corruption searchlight on every sector of Nigerian society most especially now that it has been established that corruption is a serious problem in the nation. The media are at the vanguard of the struggle and for the struggle to be meaningful, impactful and effective and the state of health of journalists, as well as the media organizations they work for, as regard their standing on anti-corruption crusade should be determined.

The involvement of media in anti-corruption crusade cut across the public and private sector of the economy either directly or indirectly. How effectively media work and report on corruption depends on a number of critical factors such as freedom of media professionals to access, verify and publish accurate information, and independence of media houses and their ability to access independent sources of financing, competition, outreach and credibility of media are other important factors affecting media performance (Nogara, 2009).

With regard to curbing corruption, the media has a dual role: to raise public awareness about corruption and to investigate and report incidences of corruption in a professional and ethical manner. In addition to having access to information, media persons ought to be able to muster courage to investigate and report without any fear of reprisals or intimidation by the corrupt. But contrary to this, media persons have been harassed, assaulted, arrested and even killed for exposing corruption. The role of the Nepalese media in the post 1990s has been praiseworthy in exposing scams related to Dhamija, Lauda Air and most recently the networking business of Unity Life International, but the buck doesn't stop here. The media should be more vibrant and vigilant during the political transition and post-conflict scenario, which is considered a fertile ground for corruption. Therefore, the media is crucial to creating and maintaining an atmosphere in public life that discourages fraud and corruption.

Successful anti-corruption programmers are dependent on knowledge and information including leadership plus collective action. The importance of information and involvement of free media including civil society against corruption can neither be downplayed nor be denied. The role of the media is vital in promoting good governance and controlling corruption. It not only raises public awareness about corruption, its causes, consequences and possible remedies but also investigates and reports incidences of corruption and irregularity. The effectiveness of the media, in turn, depends on access to information and freedom of expression, as well as a professional and ethical cadre of investigative journalists.

Theoretical Review

Agenda Setting Theory of Media

Walter Lipman [1922] propounded the 'Agenda-setting theory' argues that the Mass Media creates images of events in our minds and that policy-makers should be cognizant of those 'pictures in people's heads. Cohen [1963] also notes that the press may not be successful most of the times in telling people what to think, but is successful in telling people what to think about. The theory implies that the Mass Media pre-determine what issues are regarded as important at given time in a given society. It also ascribe to the Media, not only the power to determine what we are actually thinking, but it does ascribe to them the power to determine what we are thinking about. The elements involved in this theory include: the quantity or frequency of reporting of such issues, the prominence given to the reports through headline display, pictures and layout in newspapers or timing on radio and television. Thus the Media shape not direct opinions about a topic but rather the very topics that were seen as important enough to have opinions about. For example, individuals watching the news on Television or reading Newspaper would agree that corruption is an important issue of today. The Mass media should utilize this power of agenda-setting theory to expose all those involved in corrupt practices in Nigeria, as same time educate and enlighten the public on the negative impacts of corruption on the peace and development of Nigeria.

Observational Learning and Imitation Behavior Theory

Folarin, [2002:82] asserts that both theories assume that people, especially children, tend to learn from the mass media and to model their behavior on that of the Dramatis personae. The process is similar to that by which children imitate the behavior of adults around them. This theory has proved that how people behave in a society depends on how they see and perceive others behave. If the prevailing behavior in a country is bad, others could imitate the behavior. However the lousy argument would be that others do the same. This was one of the cited "reasons" for corrupt behavior when the Italian parliament investigated "the linkage between corruption and the Mafia in 1993". Thus, corrupt behavior encourages other corrupt behavior, especially, when the culprits go unpunished.

Concept Analysis, Definitions and Explanations

Concept of Mass Media

The mass media referred to in this study are the print media, electronic media and social media. The print media has been in existence for over a hundred years and is made up of printable items such as newspaper, magazine, books, pamphlets, journals, etc. The electronic media is made up of the radio and

television which have an advantage of sound/visual, respectively. The social media came into existence after the introduction of the Information and Communication Technology.

The Information and Communication Technology brought about a convergence among the different mediums which to the existence of the new media, a platform that made the gate keeping role of the mass media non-existent., Nwaobi, G. (2004). The media is known as the fourth arm of government, the intermediary between the Public and the government i.e. the media is referred to as the agent of change, it is independent and they are the transmitters of values good or bad. The media is the orchestrator of change; the media has effect on the behavioral pattern of the citizens of a country. It is an institution of the society, the media has certain major roles respectively to entertain, educate and to inform. When discharging their obligations they are bound by certain rules or guidelines, this is used to also check or control misuse.

Efforts of the Mass Media to Combat Corruption in Nigeria

A search through Nigerian Newspapers and Magazines in the last nine years of new democratic experiment show that corruption and corruption related matters are among issues that take up sizeable percentage of spaces available in newspapers and new magazines. Major Nigerian Newspapers usually carry between five to ten corruptions related new stories per edition. Most of editorial opinions and news features also deal with issues of fighting the scourge of corruption and enthroning transparency in government businesses. New Magazines such as The News and Tell and some newspapers including The Guardian, The Nation, Punch, Tribune, Vanguard, This Day and indeed virtually all Nigeria's independent dailies have been in the fore front of exposing corruption in high places through, obtaining hard facts through painstaking investigative journalism.

The effect of the relentless media war on corruption in Nigeria was the report by the Transparent International (TI) that Nigeria has improved noticeably in its Corruption Perception Index (CPI). Latest report of the TI, the global CPI 2008 indicated that, Nigeria ranked 121 out of 180 countries surveyed, moving seven points up and obtained a score of 2.7 out of a possible 10. Nigeria also ranked 22nd out of the 47 countries. This is an improvement compared to 148 position in 2007 and 153 in 2006 out of 180. Some of the various ways the Print Media have contributed to the fight against corruption and their effects which are examined below:

The Nigerian news media, especially the Print Media have been unrelenting in carrying news reports on corruption related matters. In fact this is the most important way the press has helped in anti-corruption crusade. Through collaboration with the anti-corruption with the anti-graft and other law enforcement agencies, the press has exposed corruption by many highly and lowly placed officials. Such reports in the press have led to removal, resignation and prosecution of highly placed officials including the former Inspector General of Police, Mr. Tafa Balogun, the former Senate President, Adolphus Wabara with former Minister Prof. Fabian Osuji and officials of the Federal Ministry of Education on the N50 million bribe-for-budget scandal, former Speaker Mrs. Patricia Olubunmi Etteh on house refurbishing deal, former Ministers (Prof Grange and Mr. Gabriel Aduku) and officials of the Federal Ministry of Health on the N300 million unspent allocation and many more. Although, the daughter of the former President Senator Iyabo Obasanjo-Bello accused along with the health Ministry officials is still functioning as a Senator, she is also charged to court. Several of the immediate past state governors and ministers are already being prosecuted while many others past and serving are still serving under investigation.

The press has also helped in unearthing corruption through investigative reporting thereby prompting anti-graft agencies to launch investigation into such matters. A ready example is the allegation of financial impropriety leveled against the former Deputy National Chairman of the ruling People's Democratic Party (PDP Chairman. He was alleged to have spearheaded a monumental mismanagement of funds of the Nigerian Port Authority (NPA) when he was chairman of the authority. Although the investigation was conducted and concluded by

EFCC under erstwhile Chairman of EFCC, Mallam of the accused to the seat of power, if not for the exposure of the investigation and its conclusions by The News Magazine and related reports by many other news media.

Another very relevant case is the allegation of secret telephone conversation against chairman justice Thomas Narvon and members of the Osun State first Elections Tribunal who were said to be involved in secret telephone conversation with one of the counsel in the matter before them. This is regarded as illegal, unethical and a gross misconduct in administration of justice. With the report, The News Magazine has opened a new window in investigative journalism from the angle of advantages offered by the GSM technology. The case is currently being investigated by the EFCC and other security agencies.

However, a corrupt press cannot fight corrupt individuals. Corruption in the media circle in Nigeria is prevalent because of the brown envelope syndrome in media practice. A major corrupt practice in the Nigerian media is the acceptance of monetary inducement popularly referred as “brown envelope”. It is perhaps the most popular source of corruption in the media. The brown envelope as a form of financial gratification is viewed by most people as a form of bribe paid by news sources to journalists to enable the former to get favorable new coverage. The practice is not alien to other parts of the world, though practice differs from place to place. For example, it is normally called brown envelope in Nigeria, but there are as well a couple of other names that the practice is called among Nigerian journalists such as “matter”, “load”, “ego”, “chopay or choppe”, “kolanut.” (Okoye, 2001).

It is any form of gratification which a journalist may receive to cover an event or influence the judgment of a journalist. The event may be a press conference, an interview of any sort, a workshop, an impromptu or organized briefing. Basically, the coinage “brown envelope” evokes the idea of criminality in the mind of right thinking persons. It is believed in many quarters that media practitioners are guilty of allegations of bribery and corruption and that acceptance of monetary gratification affects in no small measure objective coverage of news events. Journalists are usually accused of biased reporting and prejudice by members of the public because of their ignoring one of the most important attributes of good journalism that is, ‘objectivity’.

Observed Limitations of the Nigerian Mass Media in the War against Corruption

Despite the commendable contributions of the media to the anti-graft war, it is however important to print out the level of development of the Nigerian printed press may constitute hindrance to its effective performance of its roles as a major anti-corruption watchdog. The level of the industry’s economic development, for example is still poor. Most media organizations are under-capitalized. To survive, most houses depend heavily on advertisements from the same institutions and governments they are to watch. Also, in some media houses, many months of salaries are owed staff and where regularly paid, they are too low for any meaningful existence. This near-beggar status of media houses and their staff cannot ensure strict adherence to the ethics of the profession.

Closely related to low economic strength is the issue of corruption in the media itself. The media corruption takes the form of accepting ‘gifts’ from individuals, corporate bodies as well as governments and agencies of governments. Extreme cases are when journalists expect gratifications, especially in form of brown envelopes, for covering assignments and writing reports. These and related unethical conducts are very prevalent in developing countries of the world, constituting a great impediment to the exercise of functions assigned constitutionally to the media. Business, political, group and personal interests of media owners are sometimes very important clog in the wheel. In situations where media ownership is concentrated and not diverse enough, it will be easy to prevent ‘damaging’ news items injuries to the health of such interests from seeing the light of the day.

It is unfortunate that the National Assembly of Nigeria is still dragging its feet on the passage of the Freedom of Information (FOI) Bill. Despite the relative press freedom enjoyed in Nigeria, government’s activities to a large extent are still shrouded in secrecy. Many documents that could be useful in

unearthing corrupt practices are easily classified as official secret. This area would have been addressed by the FOI bill.

Stapenhurst (2000) observed that “Generally, governments have little difficulty in providing information to the public that reflects well on itself. The problem arises, by contrast, when the information reflects the opposite; here, a “voluntary disclosure by government” approach often does not work as both politicians and bureaucrats often try to hide embarrassing information”. A very important limitation to effective fight against corruption which is often overlooked is the closeness that often develops between the press and anti-graft agencies. It is observed earlier that there is a symbolic relationship between the two. Such relationship often leads to closeness and the problem is that when corruption creeps into such anti-grafts agencies, of course this is very possible, or other forms of scandal breaks out, it may be difficult for the media to report such with the same commitment and intensity required.

It also important to point out the need for adequate training is required for many journalists. The fear of some of the opponents of the FOI bill stemmed from the visible quacks in the profession who have been giving journalism a bad name. Such quacks are not necessarily trained in the basics of profession especially the observance of mass media law and ethics.

Strategies for Effective Media War against Corruption

The world Anti- corruption Watchdog:

The transparency International, reported in its recent anti- corruption handbook that a free and independent media is one of the principal vehicles for informing the public about corrupt activity. It noted that by investigating and reporting on corruption, the media provides an important counterpoint to be abuse of entrusted power for private gain, shedding light on the wrongdoing of public office holders and corporate executives alike. As such, it significantly contributes to the basis of knowledge with which citizens can hold both public and private institutions to account. However, for the media to effectively discharge these important duties as indicated above and wage a successful war against corruption, it must necessarily be armed with the tools and ingredients of the profession. Independence of the media is not only desirable but a very important factor in the fight against corruption. The political leadership of a nation desirous of fighting corruption must ensure that legislations are put in place to ensure free and unfettered press.

Whistle Blowing:

The press has also helped in unearthing corruption through investigative reporting thereby prompting anti-graft agencies to launch investigation into such matters. A ready example is the allegation of financial impropriety leveled against the former Deputy National Chairman of the ruling People’s Democratic Party (PDP Chairman. He was alleged to have spearheaded a monumental mismanagement of funds of the Nigerian Port Authority (NPA) when he was chairman of the authority. Although the investigation was conducted and concluded by EFCC under erstwhile Chairman of EFCC, Mallam of the accused to the seat of power, if not for the exposure of the investigation and its conclusions by The News Magazine and related reports by many other news media. Another very relevant case is the allegation of secret telephone conversation against chairman justice Thomas Narvon and members of the Osun State first Elections Tribunal who were said to be involved in secret telephone conversation with one of the counsel in the matter before them. This is regarded as illegal, unethical and a gross misconduct in administration of justice. With the report, The News Magazine has opened a new window in investigative journalism from the angle of advantages offered by the GSM technology.

Reinforcement of Anti- Graft values:

The press, through the consistent reports and news analysis on anti- corruption issues has helped in reinforcing values of honesty and integrity in the society. The press has constituted itself to a positive force which has

etched anti- corruption crusade in the consciousness of the people. Of course, corruption could not be said to have reduced drastically as there are dearth of ready statistics to support this, it could however be said that anti-corruption issues have been brought into the front burner of national discuss.

Corruption Deterrent:

The very consciousness among the people that there exists a vibrant press that is ever watching to report corruption inclined officials and individuals. Transparency International noted recently that ‘‘A Tradition of hard- hitting investigative journalism may, for instance, place an indirect check on corruption that might otherwise take place in the absence of informed public debate’’.

Generation and Sustenance of public support for Anti- Corruption Agencies:

A symbiotic relationship often exists between the press and the anti- graft agencies, i.e. the ICPC and EFCC. While the press depends on the agencies’ reports and findings to put together juicy, and often dramatic news reports, the agencies also enjoy adequate public presence and coverage. The report of activities of the agencies has mobilized support for them and their officers to the extent that they are now seen as heroes and heroines of some sort.

Media Tools Used for Anti- Corruption Crusade:

According to United Nations on Drugs and Crime (2004) office on Drugs and Crime report, the following tools are used by media to fight corruption:

Internet: The potential impact of the internet on awareness- raising is huge. It is an inexpensive medium and global in readership. Its wide appeal, influence and use are evident. Even though totalitarian Governments, aware of its potential to carry news that cannot be censored, have tried to find ways to restrict internet access, their efforts will probably be unsuccessful, as technology seems to outpace such efforts. Government should post their National integrity Action plan, together with regular updates on implementation and results to internet web sites. That would not only allow the plan to be widely broadcast, but it would also allow public to monitor implementation.

Survey and integrity Workshop results should similarly be published on web sites. Such data provide the public with information regarding public perceptions about corruption and the training measures used to prevent it. The Internet can be used to facilitate Broad participation of interested parties in the dissemination of important and timely information and thereby strengthens awareness globally. In that regard, the internet can contribute to minimizing duplication and sharing relevant experience.

Yet, as much as the Internet can serve as an extremely efficient and cost effective means of raising awareness and fostering discussion around the globe, a huge target audience of key stakeholders has no access. The Internet remains primarily a utility of the North with very few people from the South and from poor developing nations having ready access. There is still the need to use printed media, radio and television to reach those people.

Media Campaigns: In addition to the Internet, media campaigns should be used to disseminate anti-corruption information. A typical media campaign would include advertisements in newspapers, journals or magazines on posters, radio and TV. Leaflets could be handed out in highly frequented areas, such as pedestrian precincts, mass meetings and sporting events. Just as with any other type of advertising, short sentences and easy- to remember phrases can help make people more aware of the issues. The Nigeria writers are not left out in the anticorruption crusade [Griswold 2000).

Concept of Corruption

Corruption is mainly seen as, “wrongdoing by those in a special position of trust. The term is said to apply to self-benefiting behavior exhibited by public officials and all those dedicated to public services. Frisch [1996] observes that, “corruption is the abuse of public power for personal ends”. Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary [2000], defines corruption as a dishonest or illegal behavior, especially of people in authority.

Corruption is a major issue in the world and the problem is crucial in most developing countries such as Nigeria. However, most observers in Nigeria are getting worried because corruption is fast becoming a way of life. It is true that corruption is a worldwide phenomenon, elements of corruption are found in almost all countries of the world. However, it must be said that the incidences of corruption are much more prevalent in developing countries like Nigeria. As noted by Anderson, James H. et al (1999) in ‘The impact of corruption on the poor in Transition. The conditions of these countries are such that corruption is likely to have different causes and consequences than in more developed countries. The socio- economic conditions in low income countries are more conducive to the growth of corruption. Corruption is a symptom of deep- rooted economic and political weaknesses and shortcomings in the legislative and judicial system of the country. To aggravate the situation, accountability in these countries is generally weak, the chances of being caught are small and the penalties when caught are light”.

The inference is that it is almost impossible for the low income country to join the league of developed nations if corruption is not effectively tackled *stapenhurt (2000)*, In a corrupt system, characteristics such as infrastructural decay, lack of patriotism, subjugation of collective interests, improper implementation of policies and programmes and a disconnection between vision and its realization are prevalent. So, far Nigeria hoping to become one of the 20 most developed economies in the world by the year 2020, the fight against corruption must be one of the topmost priorities of the Government at all levels. Instructively, it has been noted by scholars that the position of Nigeria as the sixth largest exporter of oil in the world is a big contradiction to the unacceptable level of the poverty and squalor in the land. Indeed, the major reason for this sorry level of the nation’s development could be easily traced to the high incidence of corruption in *the country*.

Bayou Onangua, Editor- in Chief of The News and PM News noted recently that in many studies conducted on Nigeria, corruption has been found to be greatest problem militating against the nation’s social and economic progress. The successful strategies to curb corruption will have to simultaneously seek to reduce an official’s monopoly power through-oriented reforms, discretionary power through administrative reforms and enhance public accountability by empowering watchdog agencies such as the media and civil society. A critical element of a country’s anti-corruption strategy or programme should be an effective media. The strategies should comprise a system of checks and balances, designed to conflicts of interest arise or have a negative impact on the common good. They embody a comprehensive package of reform, addressing corruption in the public sector through government processes of leadership codes, organizational change, and through civil society participation in the democratic process of an oversight mechanism against corruption.

Factors Influencing Corruption

- Wage Considerations: a) inadequate pay b) fringe benefits and other financial incentives
- Inefficient internal control: a) inadequate supervision and control systems b) lack of explicit standard of performance for employees and organizations c) Poor recruitment and selection procedures for personnel d) too few or too many (non-transparent) rules and procedures (red tape), Ayoola [2008]
- Insufficient external control: a) law and order, tradition, checks and balances b) lack of information made available to the public and freedom of press c) mechanisms for citizen’s participation and complaint d) difficulty of proving cases in court e) high social acceptance of corruption
- Statutory penalty rate: a) amount of fine, prison sentence b) administrative sanctions c) prohibition of being ever re-employed in the public sector d) penalties for relatives

- Amount of distortions or opportunities in the economy: a) pervasive government regulations b) high statutory tax rates, non-transparent tax regulations c) provision of government services short of demand (government monopolies) Akinsele (2000).
- Other factors: a) cultural factors b) culture of bureaucratic elitism and education of civil servants d) leadership e) ethnic diversity

Causes of Corruption in Nigeria

- Several reasons have been adduced for corruption in Nigeria, one of which is the sudden disappearance of good moral and ethical values. Nwaobi (2004) affirms that Nigeria must be one of the very few countries in the world where a man's source of wealth is of no concern to his neighbors, the public or the government. Wealthy people who are known to be corrupt are regularly courted and honored by communities, religious bodies, social clubs and other private organizations. The most annoying thing is that honest and dedicated public servants, who have not accumulated dirty wealth, do not command much respect from the society. These attitudes serve to encourage a new-breed of public servants who engage in corrupt practices.
- A weak enforcement mechanism (e.g. lack of judicial independence; weak prosecutorial institutions) is another major cause of corruption in Nigeria. The forces, which deter corruption, are often weak as some, if not most, of the law enforcement agencies are themselves corrupt. In addition, rulers, politicians and civil servants are highly corrupt, and professional organizations may be in capable of sanctioning their members (Sowumi, 2004).
- It is also clear that the process of gaining power in Nigeria is either by armed force or the influence of money. Jimo & Wade (2001) attributed corruption in Nigeria to over-centralization of power, lack of media freedom to expose scandals, the impunity of well-connected officials, and absence of transparency for public fund management.
- The lack of ethical standards throughout the agencies of government and business organizations in Nigeria is another reason. Bowman [1991] contends that ethics is action, the way we practice our values; it is a guidance system to be used in making decisions. Extended family pressures and 'polygamous household are other reasons, Onalaja & Onalaja [1997], the influence of extended family system and pressure to meet family obligations are more in less developed societies. Lawrence Harrison acknowledged that the extended family system "is an effective institution for survival", but notes that it poses a big "obstacle for development.

Effects of Corruption in Nigeria

Corruption is the major among other variables that are disintegrating the Nigeria's reputation. This has demolished the image of the country and caused a lot of problems for the government and the good citizens of the nation. Many people have been caught in Europe, America and other parts of the world engaging in a corruptible act in one way or another such as: fraudulent, drug trafficking, child and women are trafficking etc. These crimes have a damaging effect on socio-economic, political aspect etc in the country. Corruption tarnishes the image of a nation; perhaps, Nigeria suffers more than most societies from her inability to deal with bribery and corruption Ali, and, Isse (2003).

In 1996 Study of Corruption by the Transparency International and Gottingen University ranked Nigeria as the most corrupt nation among the 54 nations on the study, with Pakistan as the second highest. Moore, [1997] in 1998 Transparency International Corruption Perception Index [CPI] survey of 85 countries, Nigeria was ranked 81, Lipset and Lenz [2000]. While, in 2001 survey ranked Nigeria 90 out of the 91 countries studied [second most corrupt nation in the world] with Bangladesh coming first.

Mauro, [1997], contends that corruption negatively impacts the economic growth and reduces public spending on education. The effect of corruption on education is well stated in statement made by Costello, [2001] at a

European Commission [EC] meeting in support of Nigeria's anti-poverty efforts says that Nigeria has enough money to tackle its poverty challenges. If the government can win this [its] battle against corruption and mismanagement, the money will be effectively utilized to functioning schools, health services and water supply, thus laying the foundation to eradicate poverty",

Dike, [2003], Lipset & Lenz [2000] have tied poverty and income inequalities to corruption and opine that corruption reduces the size of a nation's economic cake' thereby exposing some segments of the population to poverty. Because of corruption, Nigeria and her abundance material and human resources is ranked 26th poorest nation in the entire globe. Corruption is politically destabilizing and it leads to social revolution and military takeovers. Bribery and corruption create the culture of late payment and delays and refusal to pay for services already executed in Nigeria.

Concept of Anti-Corruption Crusade Initiatives in Nigeria

The Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission

1. Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC)
2. Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB)
3. Office of the Ombudsman
4. The Auditor General
5. Nigerian Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (NEITI)
6. Budget Monitoring and Price Intelligence Unit (BMPIU)
7. E-Governance
8. Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission (NIPC) Public Procurement
9. Whistle-Blowing

Private Anti-Corruption Initiatives:

- Information Network
- Media
- The Convention on Business Integrity (CBI)
- Zero-Corruption Coalition (ZCC)
- Independent Advocacy Project (IAP)
- Transparency International Nigeria

Kew (2006), assert that all efforts are a façade of genuine measures to promote good governance through the eradication of corrupt practices. Despite all these measures, corruption continues unabated with its adverse effects manifesting on the economy despite the abundant resources.

Way forward

1. One of the ways forward is to educate and enlighten the public through public education programme by the Nigerian mass media
2. inform citizens about their rights to services and their responsibility to avoid and report corrupt practices;
3. The public- education programme should include detailed information about free access to information, existing complaint mechanisms and results of anti- corruption efforts.
4. The public must learn:
 - Not to pay bribes themselves;
 - To report incidents of corruption to the authorities
 - Not to sell their vote; and
 - To teach their children the right values.

Conclusion

Media are crucial players in changing culture toward more transparency and accountability. By changing perceptions of what is right and wrong, the media can affect the norms that society is built on. Changes in norms will, over time, initiate changes in behavior. This, in turn, can lead to less tolerance for corruption, stronger vigilance, and stronger participation in anti-corruption efforts. However, mass media have veritable weapon in curbing corruption which can be seen, for instance, in the Philippines, investigative reporting on the president's illegal assets led to his outing. In India, reporters uncovered deeply entrenched corruption in the defense industry and motivated many other reporters to use similar methods. Currently, a movement against corruption is sweeping through the country, which could not possibly be as successful as it is if the media were not covering it extensively.

Recommendations

- The role of the media is critical in efforts against corruption. As a result, there must be careful structuring of the relationship between mass media and anti-corruption officials
- The media should be encouraged to develop and enforce adequate standards of conduct regarding their professional competence and their objectivity so that they would avoid any temptations of accepting gifts, envelopes, fare or any other support that would interfere with their free reporting.
- Since, there are enough rules to prevent corruption; the application of such rules should be applied in a blanket form, and not randomly. This will instill fear into all the stakeholders.
- Organizations engaged in the fight against corruption can use media as allies and as vehicle for their work to improve their chances of success, their effectiveness, and their sustainability.
- To use the media, organizations need to be aware of the way people use the media and of the way the media works. Understanding these two aspects will enable organizations to communicate with specific audiences to increase their awareness corruption and to mobilize them to support to fight it.
- Moreover, training in investigative journalism as area of specialization is imperative for journalist in war against corruption.

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